

1 **An expression screen to identify genes involved in chronic kidney disease.**

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7 Kidney failure is among the ten leading causes of death in the United States. Primary causes of kidney
8 failure include chronic kidney disease (resulting in end-stage renal failure), diabetic nephropathy (kidney
9 damage from diabetes) and kidney disease resulting from hypertension (high blood pressure). We
10 conducted an expression screen for discovery of genes important for chronic kidney disease in humans.

11 Citations

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